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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF EMULGEL USING
HIBISCUS LEAF EXTRACT****B. MOUNIKA¹, I. BALA TRIPURA SUNDARI²**¹B. Mounika, Department of pharmaceutics, Osmania University, Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy, Madhapur, Hyderabad-500081, Telangana State, India.²I. Bala Tripura Sundari, Assistant Professor, Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy, Madhapur, Hyderabad-500081, Telangana State, India.**Abstract****Aim:** The study was formulation and evaluation of emulgel using leaf extract of Hibiscus.**Methods:** The emulsions were prepared by using different oils like light liquid paraffin, coconut oil, olive oil and by using varying concentrations of Tween80 and Span80. The best selected emulsion was formulated into emulgel by using different gelling agents like Carbopol934, HPMC K4M, HPMC E15, NaCMC in different ratios. All the formulations were evaluated for their physicochemical parameters and percentage drug release.**Results:** The % drug release of the final optimized emulgel (OEG 4) was found to be 82.52% within 5 hours. The stability studies were performed as per ICH guidelines two different temperatures for 3months i.e., room temperature ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60\pm 5\%\text{RH}$) and ($40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75\pm 5\%\text{RH}$). The drug content of the optimized formulation OEG4 was monitored for a period of 90days.**Conclusion:** The present study revealed Hibiscus emulgel as an efficient drug delivery system for herbal extract.**Key words:** Carbopol934, HPMC E15, HPMC K4M, NaCMC, Hibiscus, Emulgel, emulsion.**Corresponding author:****B. Mounika,**

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INTRODUCTION:

In the past few decades, considerable attention has been focused on the development of drug delivery system for herbal drugs. Herbal drugs are becoming more popular in the modern world for their application to cure variety of diseases with less toxic effects and better therapeutic effects. Herbal drug carriers cure particular disease by targeting exactly the affected zone inside a patient's body and transporting the drug to that area. The drug delivery system is advantageous in delivering the herbal drug at predetermined rate and delivery of drug at the site of action which minimizes the toxic effects with increase in bioavailability of drugs. In corporation of herbal drugs in the delivery system also aids to increase in solubility, enhanced pharmacological activity, improved tissue macrophage distribution, sustained delivery and protection from physical and chemical degradation. However some limitations of herbal extracts/plant actives like instability in highly acidic pH, liver metabolism etc. led to drug levels below therapeutic concentration in the blood resulting in less or no therapeutic effect. In order to overcome this various drug delivery systems such as Emulgel, liposomes, niosomes, microspheres and phytosomes have been formulated for the delivery of herbal drugs. Incorporation of novel drug delivery technology to plant actives minimizes the presystemic metabolism, degradation of drug in the gastrointestinal tract, distribution / accumulation of drug in the non-targeted tissues and organs, and hence, reduces the side effects and improves the therapeutic efficacy and ultimately, the patient compliance[1].

EMULGEL:

Emulgels are emulsions, either of the oil-in-water or water-in-oil type, which are gelled by mixing with a gelling agent. They have a high patient acceptability since they possess the advantages of both emulsions and gels. They have been used as vehicles to deliver various drugs to the skin. A highly hydrated gel network of the hydrophilic polymers forms and liposomes are immobilized within the gel network thus mechanically stabilized. This stabilization via gelation of the continuous aqueous phase can also be applied to other dispersed systems, e.g. Suspensions or emulsions. Emulgel is a formulation with an analogous emulsion/hydrogel combination. Emulsified gel is stable one and better vehicle for hydrophobic or water insoluble drugs. Drugs may be

dissolved in the oil core or incorporated into the oil/water interface according to their lipophilicity. Emulgel can produce therapeutic local concentrations of drug in the area of inflammation, without substantial systemic absorption. Emulgel is more effective than regular gel with early cure. It is a topical percutaneous formulation of drug in a hydrophilic/lipophilic gel base. The drug penetration depth is more with the Emulgel[2].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of Plant material and Preparation of extract

Hibiscus rosa sinensis linn leaves were collected from local market, Hyderabad, India and were further authenticated by DR. Madhava Chetty, Botanist, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh. All the other solvents and reagents were of analytical grade. Fresh leaves of the plant were washed with water immediately after collection. These were chopped into small pieces, air dried at room temperature for 10 days, grounded in to fine powder and stored in air tight containers. 650 grams of powder was macerated with 5 liters pure methanol for 7 days at room temperature. Later it was filtered and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure below 50° C in rotary vacuum evaporator. It was kept in petri dish for air drying to remove the traces of methanol and finally a concentrated extract is formed[4,5].

PREPARATION OF EMULGEL:

The preparation of emulsion, first the oil phase of the emulsion was prepared by dissolving Span80 in light liquid paraffin while the aqueous phase was prepared by dissolving Tween80 in purified water. Methyl paraben and Propyl paraben were dissolved in propylene glycol whereas extract was dissolved in water, by sonication and both the solutions were separately heated to 70-75° C. Then the oily phase was added to the aqueous phase with continuous stirring until cooled to room temperature. The obtained emulsion was mixed with the gel. All the polymers (Carbopol 934, HPMC E15, HPMCK4Mand Na CMC) were used at the percentage of 0.5%-4% for the formulation of Emulgels. In this type of Emulgel preparation, the gels were formulated by dispersing 0.5, 0.75, 1%, 2%,3%,4% of different polymers in purified water with constant stirring by using homogenizer, pH of the gel was adjusted using Triethanolamine.

Table –I : Preparation of Light liquid paraffin Emulsion

Ingredients	LP1	LP2	LP3	LP4	LP5	LP6	LP7	LP8	LP9	LP10
Liquid paraffin(ml)	1	1.5	1	1.5	1.5	2	2.5	2	3	2.5
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
Water(up to 10ml)	q.s									

Table-II: Preparation of Coconut oil Emulsion

Ingredients	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10
Coconut oil(ml)	1	1.5	1	2	2.5	3	2	2.5	3	2
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3
Water(up to 10ml)	q.s									

Table-III: Preparation of Olive oil Emulsion

Ingredients	O1	O2	O3	O4	O5	O6	O7	O8	O9	O10
Olive oil (ml)	1	1.5	1.5	1.5	2	2.5	2	2.5	3	3
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3
Water(up to 10ml)	q.s									

The optimized emulsions LP5, C3, O3 were named as LP(Liquid Paraffin), C(Coconut Oil) and O(Olive oil).

Table-IV: Formulation of Carbopol934 (Light liquid paraffin) Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	LPEG1	LPEG2	LPEG3	LPEG4	LPEG5
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tween80(ml)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Carbopol934(gm)	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.3	0.4
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table-V: Formulation of HPMC E15 (Light liquid paraffin) Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	LPEG6	LPEG7	LPEG8	LPEG9
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tween80(ml)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
HPMC E15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table-VI: Formulation of Na CMC (Light liquid paraffin) Emulgels (w/w %):

INGREDIENTS	LPEG10	LPEG11	LPEG12	LPEG13
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tween80(ml)	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	15	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Na CMC(gm)	1.5	2	2.5	3
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table-VII: Formulation of Carbopol934 (coconut oil) Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	CEG1	CEG2	CEG3	CEG4	CEG5
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250	250
Coconut oil(ml)	01	01	01	01	01
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Carbopol934(gm)	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.3	0.25
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –VIII: Formulation of Na CMC (Coconut oil) Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	CEG6	CEG7	CEG8	CEG9
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Coconut oil(ml)	1	1	1	1
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	15	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Na CMC(gm)	1.5	2	2.5	3
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –IX: Formulation of HPMC E15 (Coconut oil) Emulgels (w/w%)

INGREDIENTS	CEG10	CEG11	CEG12	CEG13
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Coconut oil(ml)	1	1	1	1
Tween80(ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanol amine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
HPMC E15(gm)	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4
Water up to 20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –X: Formulation of carbopol934 (Olive oil) Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	OEG1	OEG2	OEG3	OEG4	OEG5
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250	250
Olive oil(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Tween80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
Carbopol934(gm)	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.3	0.4
Water up to20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –XI: Formulation of HPMC E15 Olive oil Emulgels (w/w %)

INGREDIENTS	OEG6	OEG7	OEG8	OEG9
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1	1	1	1
Tween80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
HPMC E15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.4
Water up to20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –XII: Formulation of HPMC K4M Olive oil Emulgels (w/w%)

INGREDIENTS	OEG10	OEG11	OEG12	OEG13
Drug(mg)	250	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1	1	1	1
Tween80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s
HPMC K4M(gm)	0.2	0.3	0.35	0.4
Water up to20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s	q.s

Table –XIII: OPTIMIZED FORMULATIONS

INGREDIENTS	LPEG4	CEG3	OEG4
Drug(mg)	250	250	250
Light liquid paraffin(ml)	1.5	-	-
Coconut oil(ml)	-	01	-
Olive oil(ml)	-	-	1.5
Tween80(ml)	0.4	0.2	0.3
Span80(ml)	0.2	0.3	0.3
Methyl paraben	0.002	0.002	0.002
Propyl paraben	0.003	0.003	0.003
Propylene glycol(ml)	1.5	1.5	1.5
Triethanolamine(q.s)	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S
Caropol934(gm)	0.3	0.2	0.3
Water up to20ml	q.s	q.s	q.s

EVALUATION OF EMULGELS:

Prepared Emulgels of Hibiscus were evaluated for physical examination parameters like colour, homogeneity, phase separation, determination of pH, spreadability, viscosity, drug content, stability, *in vitro* diffusion studies.

Homogeneity:

All developed Emulgels were tested for homogeneity by visual inspection after they have been set in the container. They were tested for their appearance and presence of any aggregates, particles and fibers.

Colour: The formulations were viewed for their visual appearance and for no colour change.

Determination of pH:

pH was checked using pH meter (Systronics digital pH meter). The electrode was submersed into the formulations at room temperature and readings were noted.

Spreadability:

The spreadability of the prepared formulations was determined by measuring the spreading diameter of 1g of the Emulgel between 20×20cm glass plates after 1 min. The mass of the upper plate was standardized at 125g. The spreadability was calculated using the formula

$$S=M.L/T$$

Where, S=spreadability

M=weight tied to the upper slide

L=length of glass slide

T=time taken to separate the slide completely from each other.

Viscosity:

Viscosity determinations of the prepared formulations were carried out by Brookfield Synchroelectric viscometer (LV-DV Pro II), Spindle S64 (Small sample adapter) and the angular velocity increased from 5, 10, 50, and 100rpm and results were noted.

Drug content:

Drug content was estimated spectrometrically where 1g of the formulation was taken and dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 7.4 and kept for shaking for 1-2 hrs. The solution was passed through the Whatmann filter paper no.42 and filtered. Appropriate dilutions were done if required and the drug content was measured spectrophotometrically against phosphate buffer pH 7.4 at 278nm.

Stability Studies:

The physical stability of the developed Emulgel formulations were performed according to the ICH guidelines. The optimized formulations were stored at two different temperature range for 3 months i.e., refrigerator conditions (2 - 8±2°C) and room temperature (25±2°C). Samples were withdrawn at 30, 60, 90 day time interval and checked for the percentage drug entrapment.

***In-vitro* diffusion studies:**

The drug release studies were carried out using modified diffusion apparatus in 250ml beaker containing 100ml Phosphate buffer. Phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was placed in a 250ml beaker. The beaker was assembled on a magnetic stirrer and the medium was equilibrated at 37±0.5°C. Dialysis membrane was taken and one end of the membrane was sealed. Emulgel was applied on the dialysis membrane and other end was closed. The dialysis membrane containing the sample was suspended in the medium. Aliquots were withdrawn (5ml) at specific intervals, filtered and the medium was immediately replaced with same quantity of fresh buffer solution. The Aliquots was measured for the amount of the drug by using UV spectrophotometer at 278nm. The cumulative drug release was calculated[13].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Determination of λ_{max}: The λ_{max} of Hibiscus extract was determined in Phosphate buffer pH 7.4. 10µg/ml of drug solution was scanning in the UV range. An absorption maximum of 278nm was obtained as shown in fig 1.0

Fig 1.0: UV Scan of Hibiscus leaf extract

Standard Graph:

The standard graph of Hibiscus extract by UV spectrophotometry at 278nm is shown in the

Fig.1.1 The linear regression equation is $y=0.0365x-0.0055$. The correlation co-efficient (R^2) of the regression line is 0.9929.

Fig1.1: Calibration curve of Hibiscus in pH 7.4 Phosphate Buffer.

Drug – Excipient compatibility studies:

Drug –Excipient compatibility studies were carried out by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy analysis (Shimadzu 8400S). The IR spectrum of the

pure drug was compared with IR spectrum of combination of drug and excipient and it was found that there were no specific interactions between the drug and excipient.

Fig no.1.2 FT-IR of Hibiscus

Fig no.1.3 FT-IR of optimized formulation

Table no XIV: Functional groups of Drug-Excipient compatibilities

Functional group	Observed functional group in drug	Observed functional group in emulgel
C=C	1629.9	1629.9
S=O	1045.5	1041.6
O-H	3421.8	3421.8
N-H	3500.2	3500.2

The formulations were analysed for the homogeneity, pH, drug content and spreadability and from the obtained results it can be observed that the Emulgel formulations were found to be stable at different temperature condition

Table no XV: Homogeneity, pH, drug content and spreadability determination of emulgels

Formulation code	Homogeneity	pH	Drug Content	Spreadability (cm)
LPEG-1	++	6.8±0.03	91.1±0.02	1.8±0.10
LPEG-2	++	6.9±0.01	93.8±0.03	1.6±0.08
LPEG-3	++	6.8±0.06	94.2±0.02	2.8±0.4
LPEG-4	++	6.9±0.1	95.36±0.01	3.1±0.3
LPEG-5	++	6.8±0.12	92.9±0.06	3.0±0.3
LPEG-6	++	6.7±0.1	72.8±0.0	1.2±0.02
LPEG-7	++	6.8±0.02	67.6±0.01	1.5±0.08
LPEG-8	++	6.7±0.18	77.8±0.07	2.2±0.12
LPEG-9	++	6.8±0.02	72.2±0.04	2.6±0.18
LPEG-10	++	6.8±0.01	75.8±0.05	1.1±0.02
LPEG-11	++	6.8±0.02	68.2±0.04	1.8±0.03
LPEG-12	++	6.5±0.08	71.5±0.06	2.1±0.12
LPEG-13	++	6.7±0.09	76.2±0.05	2.4±0.16
CEG-1	++	6.8±0.02	83.5±0.09	1.7±0.09
CEG-2	++	6.8±0.03	85.1±0.03	1.9±0.06
CEG-3	++	6.9±0.18	87.4±0.05	2.0±0.12
CEG-4	++	6.8±0.12	81.5±0.06	2.8±0.15
CEG-5	++	6.8±0.1	79.6±0.06	3.0±0.16
CEG-6	++	6.1±0.01	68.6±0.04	1.6±0.06
CEG-7	++	6.9±0.11	72.2±0.06	1.2±0.12
CEG-8	++	6.1±0.08	78.6±0.08	1.8±0.08
CEG-9	++	6.7±0.06	76.6±0.07	2.1±0.12
CEG-10	++	6.8±0.02	84.5±0.08	2.6±0.18
CEG-11	++	6.8±0.12	79.8±0.05	1.2±0.06
CEG-12	++	6.7±0.09	68.9±0.04	1.6±0.12
CEG-13	++	6.8±0.02	77.7±0.06	1.2±0.02
OEG-1	++	6.9±0.09	85.5±0.06	1.7±0.17
OEG-2	++	7.0±0.1	87.2±0.08	1.8±0.18
OEG-3	++	7.1±0.2	92.6±0.07	1.6±0.12
OEG-4	++	7.2±0.2	97.28±0.08	3.2±0.31
OEG-5	++	7.0±0.08	95.3±0.07	2.8±0.14
OEG-6	++	6.9±0.09	68.5±0.05	2.9±0.16
OEG-7	++	6.8±0.03	68.6±0.06	2.1±0.12
OEG-8	++	6.9±0.06	71.2±0.07	1.2±0.09
OEG-9	++	6.2±0.01	62.8±0.06	1.6±0.06
OEG-10	++	6.4±0.08	68.2±0.07	1.4±0.08
OEG-11	++	6.5±0.06	56.9±0.05	1.2±0.12
OEG-12	++	6.7±0.09	53.2±0.05	1.9±0.18
OEG-13	++	6.8±0.02	63.3±0.06	1.3±0.13

Viscosity:

Viscosity determinations of the prepared formulations were carried out by Brookfield Synchroelectric viscometer (LV-DV Pro II), Spindle S64 (Small sample adapter) and the angular velocity increased from 5, 10, 50, and 100rpm and values were noted and represented in the table no XVI.

Table no XVI: Viscosity determination of emulgels

Emulgel	At 5 rpm (cps)	At 10 rpm (cps)	At 50 rpm(cps)	At 100 rpm (cps)
LPEG-1	4695	3652	2020	832
LPEG-2	3789	3172	1985	754
LPEG-3	3586	2896	1672	635
LPEG-4	6953	4183	1172	439
LPEG-5	5872	4112	1150	440
LPEG-6	5320	4182	1011	415
LPEG-7	4382	3156	2086	586
LPEG-8	5168	4236	3584	865
LPEG-9	6106	5128	4695	946
LPEG-10	5126	4128	3952	1025
LPEG-11	6842	5124	4286	986
LPEG-12	7584	6428	3946	982
LPEG-13	6892	5482	3698	865
CEG-1	4682	3596	2548	758
CEG-2	4258	3215	2168	724
CEG-3	5136	3648	1254	462
CEG-4	6872	4827	1142	486
CEG-5	6612	4685	1254	421
CEG-6	4258	3586	2496	786
CEG-7	5126	4258	3568	1254
CEG-8	6685	5421	4586	986
CEG-9	4286	3569	2168	864
CEG-10	4586	3684	1869	985
CEG-11	3486	2486	1125	864
CEG-12	4198	3465	2485	759
CEG-13	5846	3458	2698	984
OEG-1	5692	4852	3465	986
OEG-2	6437	5469	3125	845
OEG-3	7549	6854	4125	874
OEG-4	9842	5962	1829	1081
OEG-5	9836	5864	2135	1156
OEG-6	4896	3586	2458	1054
OEG-7	4934	3659	2896	986
OEG-8	5108	4268	3540	1286
OEG-9	6428	5487	4895	1105
OEG-10	4758	3869	2541	1059

OEG-11	4687	3897	2487	1286
OEG-12	3896	3159	2186	986
OEG-13	4168	3486	2259	997

Table no 1: Percentage drug release of (liquid paraffin emulgels) LPEG (1-5)

Time(Hrs)	%DR of LPEG1	%DR of LPEG2	%DR of LPEG3	%DR of LPEG4	%DR of LPEG5
0	0	0	0	0	0
30min	5.68	6.37	7.41	5.85	6.01
45min	9.77	10.52	12.68	10.61	10.74
1	18.27	20.14	18.73	17.85	17.05
2	27.56	36.96	35.74	34.68	31.60
3	31.48	45.32	48.62	46.41	45.82
4	45.19	54.73	56.12	58.21	54.16
5	61.14	66.41	69.85	71.18	62.18

Table no 2: Percentage drug release of (liquid paraffin emulgels) LPEG (6-9)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of LPEG6	%DR of LPEG7	%DR of LPEG8	%DR of LPEG9
0	0	0	0	0
30	4.62	3.66	3.02	4.29
1	11.28	8.91	6.16	9.73
2	22.36	17.45	18.64	19.65
3	29.37	24.72	26.91	23.15
4	35.15	30.61	32.12	30.28
5	41.02	45.73	42.65	48.68

Table no 3: Percentage drug release of (liquid paraffin emulgels) LPEG (10-13)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of LPEG10	%DR of LPEG11	%DR of LPEG12	%DR of LPEG13
0	0	0	0	0
30min	5.29	3.66	4.62	3.21
1	9.73	6.16	8.28	6.86
2	14.28	11.76	15.26	12.58
3	22.27	17.45	22.36	19.68
4	31.26	24.72	29.37	25.12
5	39.76	38.36	35.28	39.87

Table no 4: Percentage drug release of (coconut oil emulgels) CEG (1-5)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of CEG1	%DR of CEG2	%DR of CEG3	%DR of CEG4	%DR of CEG5
0	0	0	0	0	0
30	6.88	5.80	6.72	6.82	5.60
1	17.11	16.21	19.36	14.12	13.64
2	26.18	24.86	31.18	29.16	28.39
3	38.62	34.28	42.06	39.87	36.45
4	46.18	44.61	59.89	52.68	49.85
5	60.84	61.01	64.21	61.19	62.16

Table no 5: Percentage drug release of (coconut oil emulgels) CEG (6-9)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of CEG6	%DR of CEG7	%DR of CEG8	%DR of CEG9
0	0	0	0	0
30	3.26	4.10	3.86	3.75
1	9.19	10.49	9.35	10.12
2	18.12	20.38	18.66	19.46
3	26.59	27.68	26.19	26.12
4	32.54	34.16	35.48	32.18
5	41.06	42.16	41.88	39.87

Table no 6: Percentage drug release of (coconut oil emulgels) CEG (10-13)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of CEG10	%DR of CEG11	%DR of CEG12	%DR of CEG13
0	0	0	0	0
30	3.26	2.87	1.66	2.47
1	9.19	7.71	7.18	8.62
2	16.87	13.64	13.19	14.18
3	27.41	25.18	26.48	22.48
4	31.13	29.16	30.18	31.13
5	39.88	36.48	34.19	37.18

Table no 7: Percentage drug release of (olive oil emulgels) OEG (1-5)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of OEG1	%DR of OEG2	%DR of OEG3	%DR of OEG4	%DR of OEG5
0	0	0	0	0	0
30	6.37	7.41	8.15	8.82	7.68
1	15.36	18.73	21.66	28.78	22.86
2	27.86	29.46	38.15	41.18	37.92
3	39.85	41.86	49.85	54.48	49.87
4	51.74	52.88	59.12	71.18	67.12
5	68.48	71.52	73.16	82.52	81.21

Table no 8: Percentage drug release of (olive oil emulgels) OEG (6-9)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of OEG6	%DR of OEG7	%DR of OEG8	%DR of OEG9
0	0	0	0	0
30	4.47	3.81	3.04	2.44
1	9.83	8.12	8.27	8.05
2	19.67	16.44	18.54	16.88
3	26.73	24.57	27.48	26.75
4	32.38	31.68	31.88	30.64
5	39.14	38.12	39.21	36.75

Table no 9: Percentage drug release of (olive oil emulgels) OEG (10-13)

Time (Hrs)	%DR of OEG10	%DR of OEG11	%DR of OEG12	%DR of OEG13
0	0	0	0	0
30	3.85	3.61	2.95	2.40
1	9.82	9.65	8.42	6.48
2	16.84	17.48	13.81	13.21
3	25.31	21.85	24.38	21.03
4	32.01	29.68	32.41	29.38
5	38.61	37.41	41.06	38.67

Table no 10: Drug release of Optimized Emulgels

Time (Hrs)	%DR of LPEG4	%DR of CEG3	%DR of OEG4
0	0	0	0
30	5.85	6.72	8.82
45	10.61	12.88	13.58
1	17.85	19.36	28.78
2	34.68	31.18	41.18
3	46.41	42.06	54.48
4	58.21	59.89	71.18
5	71.18	64.21	82.52

Fig no 1.4: Drug release profiles of Optimized Emulgels

Stability studies: Stability studies were performed as per ICH guidelines two different temperatures for 3months i.e., room temperature ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60+5\%\text{RH}$) and ($40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75+5\%\text{RH}$). The drug content of the optimized formulations LPEG4, CEG3, OEG4 was monitored for a period of 90days.

Time period (days)	%Drug content at room temperature conditions ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60+5\%\text{RH}$)	%Drug content at room temperature conditions ($40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75+5\%\text{RH}$)
0	98.68	98.21
30	96.18	96.62
60	95.41	95.48
90	97.16	97.42

All the formulations were evaluated for their physicochemical parameters. The best selected formulation (OEG4) showed drug release of 82.52% in 5hrs. The stability studies were performed as per ICH guidelines two different temperatures for 3months i.e., room temperature ($25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/60+5\%\text{RH}$) and ($40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}/75+5\%\text{RH}$). The drug content of the optimized formulations OEG4 was monitored for a period of 90days.

CONCLUSION:

Hibiscus emulsions were successfully formulated by wet gum method. Emulsions were prepared by using different oils like light liquid paraffin, coconut oil, olive oil and by using varying concentrations of Tween80 and Span80. The best selected emulsion was formulated into emulgel by using different gelling agents like Carbopol934, HPMC K4M, HPMC E15, NaCMC in different ratios. All the formulations were evaluated for their physicochemical parameters. FTIR analysis of emulgel formulations and the drug were studied for the interaction of the excipients and the drug in the final formulation. Similar peaks were observed in spectra of optimized formulation. Absence of interfering peaks indicates that there is no unwanted reaction between the drug and excipients used in the studies.

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